

PRINCIPLES OF RUSSIAN PUNCTUATION*N. Aminboeva¹**Abstract:*

The ability to interpret the text, as many researchers rightly point out, allows one to join the author's vision of the world, enrich oneself spiritually, and improve the spiritual culture of a person. When analyzing a literary text, the dominant place is usually given to lexical and stylistic means, however, syntactic means, which have come to the fore in modern literature, play a crucial role in creating the expressiveness of the text, in understanding the main idea of the work and the author's worldview.

Key words: punctuation, punctuation marks, intonation

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/aspz4y56>

Serving the needs of written communication, punctuation has a clear purpose - to help break down the written text to make it easier to understand. The dismemberment can have different bases: formal-grammatical (taking into account the syntactic structure of the sentence and its components), semantic (reflection of the content significance of speech), intonation (distribution of pauses, logical and semantic accents, transmission of emotional nuances of speech).

In the practice of writing, the writer has to simultaneously solve two interrelated punctuation tasks: to determine the place for the punctuation marks and to select the necessary punctuation mark. Neither intonation nor semantic principles can reliably determine the place of the punctuation marks.

Modern Russian punctuation is built on the semantic and structural-grammatical foundations, which are interconnected and condition each other, so we can talk about a single semantic-grammatical basis of Russian punctuation. Punctuation reflects the semantic division of written speech, indicates semantic connections and relationships between individual words and groups of words, and various semantic shades of parts of a written text. But certain semantic connections of words and parts of the text find their expression in a certain grammatical structure.

And it is no coincidence that the formulation of most of the rules of modern Russian punctuation relies simultaneously on the semantic features of the sentence (on the semantic basis), and on the features of its structure - the features of the construction of the sentence, its parts, the presence or absence of conjunctions, ways of expressing the members of the sentence, the order of their arrangement, etc. p., which is the structural and grammatical basis of punctuation.

In specific speech situations, punctuation helps to reveal the structure, meaning and intonation of written speech. The principles operate, as a rule, simultaneously.

¹ *Aminboeva N.K., Teacher of the Tashkent State Agrarian University of the Department of the Uzbek language and literature*

But from the point of view of functional significance, they are unequal. In those cases, for example, when the intonational division of a sentence does not coincide with its grammatical division, the signs obey the semantic-syntactic principle, and intonation is not taken into account. For example, the discrepancy between intonation and punctuation always consists in the fact that the sign is present where the grammatical structure of the sentence requires it, and not the intonational pause.[11] However, in those cases where different divisions of the sentence structure are possible (and, consequently, different comprehension), it is the sign set "according to intonation" that turn out to be decisive for the comprehension of the sentence.

In a sentence, all punctuation marks delimit the semantic segments of the text: a comma separates the designations of homogeneous concepts from each other (bird of prey, beast of prey); the dash expresses the opposition of phenomena (predators that can or should be destroyed - and a friend who must be protected); the dot indicates the completeness of the thought.

All punctuation marks divide the sentence into structural and grammatical segments: a comma separates homogeneous members, a dash - two parts of an union-free complex sentence, a dot completes a declarative sentence.

Each of the signs is also "read" intonationally: the comma in this sentence requires a small pause, the same type of reading of the homogeneous members it shares, the dash indicates a significant and tense pause, a change in the tempo and tone of pronunciation of the second part; point - about a calm lowering of the voice and a long pause.

It should also be noted that the intonational division of sentences is also influenced by subjective factors: an individual manner of speaking, special goals of the statement, which can lead to a mismatch between the intonational and semantic-grammatical division of sentences.

In such cases, the punctuation marks are based on the semantic-grammatical structure of the sentence. "The formal-grammatical principle in punctuation makes punctuation rules stable and generally accepted" [33]. Only in this case, punctuation acquires social significance, contributing to the improvement of communication between the writer and the reader. The same understanding of punctuation marks helps the writer to more accurately convey his thoughts and feelings, and the reader to understand them correctly.

The predominant importance of the semantic and structural-grammatical principles of Russian punctuation should in no way reduce attention to the intonation of a sentence, since only with the ability to "read" and "hear" punctuation marks is it possible to successfully master the rules of punctuation: intonation helps to distinguish between semantic and structural segments of sentences, to identify semantic-grammatical relationships between them.

Although the Russian language has many rules for mandatory punctuation, Russian punctuation has great flexibility: there are various punctuation options that are associated not only with the meaning, but also with the stylistic features of the text.

The stability of the Russian punctuation system is explained, first of all, by the fact that the principles that define it make it possible to convey in writing both the semantic, syntactic, and, to a large extent, intonation structure of speech.

Punctuation marks in most cases divide the text into syntactic units related in meaning and intonation. For example: Terkin - who is he? Let's be honest:

he's just an ordinary guy. However, the guy though where. There is always a guy like this in every company, and in every platoon. In this text, the question mark and dots indicate the boundaries of independent syntactic units - sentences expressing in each case a relatively complete thought. These punctuation marks also characterize the purpose and intonation of the utterance and indicate large pauses at the end of the sentence.

Bibliography:

- [1]. Baranov N.T. *Russian language*. - M. 1984.
- [2]. Blinov G.I. *Punctuation problems* \ \ *Russian language* No. 1, 1987.
- [3]. Baudouin de Courtenay I.A. *Punctuation* // *Baudouin de Courtenay I.A.*
- [4]. Valgina N.S. *Punctuation* // *Code of Russian Spelling Rules. Spelling. Punctuation. Project. M., 2000.*